

PROPOSED PRINTED REMEDIATION MATERIAL IN SCIENCE FOR GRADE 10 LEARNERS

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Abstract. This study is intended to propose printed remediation material in Science for Grade 10 learners at Salinap National High School in District V- B, San Carlos City Division during the school year 2020- 2021. The evaluation results of Grade 10 Science teachers, School Science coordinator in District V-B, Education Program Supervisor in Science, and Learning Resource Management and Development System Supervisor as to the level of acceptability of the proposed printed remediation material in Science for Grade 10 learners as to content has an AWM of 3.66, as to presentation and organization, the rating is 3.76 and as to format is 3.89. All the given factors have a descriptive rating of "highly acceptable". Suggestions and recommendations from the evaluators were integrated with the finalization of the proposed printed remediation material in Science for Grade 10 learners. With this, the proposed printed remediation material is highly recommended for classroom use. It is also recommended for use by Grade 10 teachers in the district and the division level.

Keywords. Remediation Material, Acceptability Level, Non-mastered Competencies

1 Introduction

The onslaught of the COVID-19 pandemic around the globe brought dramatic changes and challenges to the global education community (Huang, 2020). Most governments have temporarily closed educational institutions as part of their measures to prevent the virus as it affects 70 percent of the world's student population (UNESCO, 2020). Different institutions and organizations around the globe-initiated projects and temporary solutions to support continuous learning. In response, the Department of Education and its supporting sectors came up with alternative learning delivery modalities which are reflected in the Adoption of The Basic Education Learning Continuity Plan for the School Year 2020-2021- In Light of the Covid-19 Public Health Emergency DepEd Order 12 s. 2020. Shared responsibility of the teachers and parents plays a vital role in effectively implementing the new learning modalities to help the learners achieve curricular goals. However, with the sudden shift of learning modality teaching and learning process becomes harder.

According to Lampard (2016), the difficulty facing teachers today is adjusting teaching methods and materials to meet a very wide range of needs. As such it is a problem, not merely of how to provide help for children who are failing, but of the means to prevent under-functioning in basic educational processes on the one hand and to provide the enrichment of wider experiences.

Since there is little to no connection between the teacher and the learners, modular distance learning is more difficult not only for the teachers but also for the students. Because of the little time allotted to develop and print the self-learning modules (SLMs), mishaps such as grammar errors, wrong math equations, and modules depicting gender stereotypes alarmed the public as they expressed concerns over the quality of education of over 24 million students during the pandemic (Magsambol, 2020). Furthermore, some learners have difficulty answering and completing modules on time due to the limited explanations provided in printed Science learning modules (SLMs) on topics that are difficult to understand, and there are additional activities to complete, some of which are not even discussed on the self-learning modules (SLMs), failing to meet the required learning competencies. Under the distance learning system, parents have an active role in guiding their children through modular lessons – which poses a problem for students who do not have anyone to facilitate learning at home, or whose parents are not capable of guiding them due to lack of knowledge.

Despite the difficulty and challenges brought about by the pandemic, the 21st century is characterized by rapid economic growth and technological changes. It is a century that is heavily based on Science and Technology which is evident in how we live nowadays (Castanega 2016). Therefore, the school has a larger share of responsibility for the development of scientific attitudes, habits, skills, and knowledge that should be attuned to be more responsive to the present needs. Moreover, to promote quality education in all areas and levels of learning, Science is frequently perceived to be of great

importance because of its link to technology and industry. Scientific literacy is important to develop students' capacity for a scientific way of thinking and to live a productive life essential to nation-building.

The Department of Education established seventy-five percent (75%) standard proficiency level of learner achievement in all learning areas but the achievement rate of learners falls below the minimum performance, particularly in Science. The researcher, as a science teacher at Salinap National High School, noticed the poor performance of Grade 10 learners in the first two quarters of the school year 2020-2021 as reflected on their summative test results. It is along this premise that the researcher was prompted to propose printed remediation material in Science for Grade 10 learners.

2 Review of Related Literature

Generally speaking, the various related studies all corroborate and have a direct bearing on the present study. The primary purpose of this study is to propose printed remediation material for Grade 10 learners in Science. In addition, the above-mentioned studies have given more impetus to propose printed remediation material that will be beneficial to learners who have difficulty mastering the required learning competencies in Science.

The studies of Dumigi and Cabrella (2019), Musongole and Chipindi (2021), Jamian (2016), Homan (2016), Asio and Jimenez (2020), Carale (2019), Ambayon and Millines (2020), and Dahar (2016) pointed out that remediation materials play a vital role in the academic performance of the learners. All their studies revealed that there is a positive result in using their innovative outputs in the performance of the students. Furthermore, all of them emphasized that remediation materials should be geared up to the learners' interests, needs, maturity, and abilities. These studies are very related to the present study because the researcher proposed printed remediation material which also aims to improve the learner's academic performance by achieving the required learning competencies through the use of printed remediation material that is suitable for those learners who are lagging.

Capuyan (2019), Guevarra (2017), Pimentel (2017), Rogayan and Albino (2019), Zhao (2021), Fill and Okey (2018), Kumawati and Tiwari (2020), Bordeos (2021), and Maawa (2019) emphasized that there is a positive effect of the remedial programs and sessions when it is based on the learning style of the learners to cater their different needs. The present study correlates to the idea of the said studies because the researcher proposed a printed remediation material that is suitable to the learner's needs but it is also different from the aforementioned studies because those are all programs and sessions for remediation which requires the teachers and learners to interact regularly while the present study is intended to the current situation which is in printed modular form based on the alternative learning modality of the learners.

In the same way, studies of Marces (2019), Oyekan (2018), Rogayan and Albino (2019), Guevarra (2019), Gowri (2020), Saunders-Harris and Yeany (2016), Arora (2021), Modi and Nair (2021) and Sacaben-Aquino (2021) are all related to the present study in terms of the learning area which is Science and all of these studies are concerned in addressing the least mastered skills and competencies of the learners. It only differs in the way how to enhance the performance, some of these studies made use of remedial programs and sessions while the present study proposed a printed remediation material.

The studies of Chen (2020), Pai (2020), Lin and Wang (2017), and Honrales (2017) emphasized the effectiveness of using Information, Communication and Technology (ICT) in remedial instruction. All of their studies showed positive effects after using their outputs. These differ in the present study because the researcher proposed a printed remediation material in printed modular form which considers the learning modality of the learners.

All studies have great roles in conducting this study for they all emphasized the importance of the appropriate selection of materials and activities to be used as remediation material to improve the learner's academic performance. The present study also gave great importance to preparing and developing remediation material used to achieve the required learning competencies.

3 Research Methodology

3.1 Research Design

This study employed the descriptive–developmental research design. This study used a descriptive method of research because it tried to describe the situation or condition during the conduct of the investigation.

It is also developmental because the researcher developed and proposed a printed remediation material for Grade 10 learners in Science. The output of the study is in a printed modular form that contains an introduction, table of contents, vocabulary time, three (3) activities with guide questions, one (1) Do it Yourself simplified hands-on activity, self-check, trivia, facts, and verses per lesson and real-life applications and evaluation per unit which help to address the not mastered competencies in Science.

3.2 Sources of Data

This study made use of data from two (2) sources. The first source of data is the summative test results of Grade 10 learners in Science during the first and second quarters of this school year 2020- 2021. The not mastered competencies were determined based on the results of the summative test in the first and second quarters during the school year 2020-2021 using the percentage correct response (PCR).

The second source of data is the evaluation results as to the level of acceptability of the proposed remediation material for Grade 10 learners in Science. The material was evaluated by Grade 10 Science teachers and School Science Coordinators in District V- B, the Educational Program Supervisor in Science and Learning Resources, Management and Development System Supervisor in the San Carlos City Division. Their involvement was in the evaluation of the proposed printed remediation material based on a given set of criteria.

3.3 Statistical Treatment of Data

To determine the not mastered competencies of Grade 10 learners in Science, an analysis of the summative test results in the first and second quarters of the school year 2020- 2021 was conducted using the percentage of correct response (PCR).

Average Weighted Mean (AWM) was utilized to analyze the answers to questions having scaled responses. The obtained frequencies for each alternative response were multiplied by the assigned weights in the selected point, from the highest to lowest. Then the sum of the products obtained was divided by the number of respondents to get the average weighted mean. The obtained weighted averages or mean was the basis for the verbal description of the responses of the evaluators to a given item.

To interpret the data gathered on the evaluation of Grade 10 Science Teachers, School Science Coordinators in District V- B, Education Program Supervisor in Science and Learning Resource Management and Development System Supervisor on the proposed printed remediation material in Science for Grade 10 learners the DepEd-LRMDS Evaluation Rating Sheet for Print Resources.

4 Presentation, Analysis, and Interpretation of Data

4.1 Not Mastered Competencies in Grade 10 to Science Based on the Analysis of the Summative Test Results During the First and Second Quarters of School Year 2020-2021

Table 1 presents the findings on the first and second quarters analysis on the summative test results during the school year 2020-2021. For the first quarter, out of the 5 most essential learning competencies in Grade 10 Science, there are 2 not mastered competencies. Results show that these 2 learning competencies are the following: Identify the different processes that occur along plate boundaries (58%); and enumerate the lines of evidence that support plate movement (59%). The findings in the second quarter reveal that out of the 6 most essential learning competencies in Science 10, there is 1 competency that was not mastered by the learners. Results show that this learning competency is to cite

examples of practical applications of the different regions of EM waves, such as the use of radio waves in telecommunications (59%).

Based on the analysis of the summative test result for the first quarter, the researcher noted that the learners were having difficulty in identifying the different processes that occur along plate boundaries since there are more than one (1) feature and process that may occur depending on the type of plate boundaries. In addition to this, the learners are also having a hard time enumerating the lines of evidence that support plate movements like the theory of Alfred Wegener and Harry Hess.

Table 1. Identified Not Mastered Competencies of Grade 10 Learners in Science Based on the Analysis of Summative Test Results in First and Second Quarters During the School Year 2020- 2021

Competencies	Percentage of Correct Response (PCR)	Descriptive Equivalent
FIRST QUARTER		
Describe the distribution of active volcanoes, earthquake, and major mountain belts	80%	Mastered
Describe the different types of plate boundaries	85%	Mastered
Identify the different processes that occur along plate boundaries	58%	Not Mastered
Describe the possible causes of plate movement	75%	Mastered
Enumerate the lines of evidence that support plate movement	59%	Not Mastered
SECOND QUARTER		
Compare the relative wavelengths of different forms of Electro Magnetic waves	76%	Mastered
Cite examples of practical applications of the different regions of Electro Magnetic waves, such as the use of radio waves in telecommunications	59%	Not Mastered
Explain the effects of Electro Magnetic radiation on living things and their environment	86%	Mastered
Predict the qualitative characteristics of images formed by plane and curved mirrors and lenses	77%	Mastered
Identify ways in which mirrors and lenses determine their optical instruments	79%	Mastered
Explain the operation of a simple electric motor and generator	76%	Mastered

4.2 Evaluation of Grade Science 10 Teachers

It is worthwhile to note that 6 out of 7 indicators for the criterion Content were rated as “highly acceptable”. Along this line, the same table above further shows that indicator number 3, as rated by Grade 10 Science teachers has the highest mean of 3.93 with a descriptive equivalent of “highly acceptable”. The indicator deals on “material provides for the development of higher cognitive skills.” This finding would suggest that as to the content, the teacher-evaluators believe that the proposed printed remediation material can provide avenues for the learners to enhance their critical thinking, creativity, learning by doing, inquiry, problem-solving, and the likes.

On the other hand, Grade 10 Science teachers rated item number 5 as “acceptable” with an AWM of 3.43. This indicator is on the “material enhances the development of desirable values and traits.” This indicator was rated as the lowest since though some values and traits are integrated into the remediation material, the researcher failed to underpin or emphasize them.

As to presentation and organization criterion, the researcher noted that all indicators were rated as “highly acceptable” with an over-average weighted mean of 3.71. Although all indicators were rated as highly acceptable, indicator number 3 stands out as it was given the highest mean of 3.93. The indicator deals on “vocabulary level is adapted to target reader’s likely experience and level of understanding”. This implies that there is a strong relationship between vocabulary knowledge and reading comprehension; learners need to understand the meaning of critical words they will be reading to promote comprehension. Vocabulary knowledge, along with background knowledge, provides learners with a better chance of understanding the text they read. It could be gleaned that the proposed printed remediation material suits the vocabulary level of the learners which helps them better understand the concepts they are reading.

4.3 Evaluation of School Science Coordinator

It could be gleaned from the table that indicator 2 as to content criterion has the highest rating of 3.89 with the descriptive equivalent of “highly acceptable”. This indicator deals with “material contributes to the achievement of specific objectives of the subject area and grade/year level for which it is intended” It shows that the proposed printed remediation material reinforces, enriches, and or leads to mastery of certain learning competencies and supports the achievement of learning objectives and outcomes in Earth Science and Physics. Looking intently at the table, indicator 5 has the lowest mean rating of 3.44. The researcher noted that the same indicator got the lowest mean rating both from Grade 10 Science teachers and School Science Coordinators. This implies that the researcher failed to properly discuss and include in the material the desirable values and traits.

Furthermore, as to presentation and organization, indicator 2 got the highest rating of 3.89 with the descriptive equivalent of “highly acceptable” This deals with “logical and smooth flow of ideas”. This shows that the proposed printed remediation material has a logical flow of ideas and a smooth and orderly progression of content which help the learners achieve the required competencies.

4.4 Evaluation of Education Program Supervisor in Science

As to presentation and organization, 4 out of 5 were rated as “highly acceptable”. It is shown on the table that only 1 indicator was rated as “acceptable” with a rating of 3. This indicator deals with the “length of sentences is suited to the comprehension level of the target reader”. Like the other evaluators, this indicator got the lowest rating. This only implies that the length of sentences in a remediation material could affect the performance of the learners. As a whole, the content, presentation, and organization as evaluated by the Education Program Supervisor both rated “highly acceptable” with a general overall rating of 3.76.

4.5 Evaluation of Learning Resource Management and Development System Supervisor

It could be gleaned from the table that 16 out of 18 indicators were rated “highly acceptable”. This would mean that the developed remediation material could help learners to understand well the ideas and concepts presented through illustrations, labels, captions, and standard sizes and fonts. The researcher noted the importance of each indicator in addressing the learning needs of the learners.

The format has an overall rating of 3.89 with the descriptive equivalent of “highly acceptable”. It could be deduced that the proposed printed remediation material in Science for Grade 10 learners could still be improved on certain criteria so that the intention to address the not mastered competencies specifically on Earth Science and Physics could be achieved.

4.6 Summary of Evaluation Results of the Proposed Printed Remediation Material in Science

The summary of evaluation results made by Grade 10 Science Teachers, School Science Coordinators in District V- B, Education Program Supervisor in Science, and Learning Resource Management and Development System Supervisor are contained in Table 4E. The evaluators made use of a given set of criteria along three (3) factors such as content, presentation and organization, and format.

It could be noted that along the three criteria content, presentation and organization, and format, the Grade 10 Science Teacher and School Science Coordinators in District V- B, Education Program Supervisor in Science and Learning Resource Management, and Development System Supervisor rated the proposed printed remediation material in Science

for Grade 10 learners as “highly acceptable” as to content, presentation and organization and format with a computed over-all average weighted mean of 3.66, 3.76 and 3.89 respectively.

As a whole, the proposed printed remediation material in Science for Grade 10 learners has a 3.78 rating with the descriptive equivalent of “highly acceptable”. Based on the LRMSD Evaluation Rating Sheet for Print Resources, this means that remediation material was able to meet all features above standards; highly recommended for approval for public utilization.

Table 2. Summary of Evaluation Results of the Proposed Printed Remediation Material in Science for Grade 10 Learners by Criterion

CRITERIA	EVALUATORS				OW AM	DE
	Grade 10 Science Teachers N=14	School Science Coordinators N=9	Education Program Supervisor in Science N=1	LRMDS Supervisor N=1		
Content	3.69	3.71	3.71		3.70	HA
Presentation and Organization	3.71	3.76	3.80		3.76	HA
Format				3.89	3.89	HA
OVAER- ALL WEIGHTED MEAN					3.78	HA

5 Conclusion and Recommendation

The not mastered competencies in Grade 10 Science based on the analysis of summative test results of the first and second quarters of the school year 2020–2021 are: 1) Identify the different processes that occur along plate boundaries (58%); 2) Enumerate the lines of evidence that support plate movement (59%); 3) Cite examples of practical applications of the different regions of EM waves, such as the use of radio waves in telecommunications (59%). The proposed printed remediation material is developed to address the not mastered competencies in Science for Grade 10 learners. Based on the evaluation of Grade 10 Science Teachers, School Science Coordinators in District V- B, and Education Program Supervisor in Science, as to the content, it was rated an AWM of 3.66 and as to presentation and organization, the AWM is 3.76. The format was rated with 3.76 as evaluated by the Learning Resource Management and Development System Supervisor. All the given criteria have a descriptive rating of highly acceptable.

There are identified not mastered competencies during the first and second quarters in Grade 10 Science for the school year 2020- 2021. The proposed printed remediation material is suitable for the use of Grade 10 learners in Science. The proposed printed remediation material in Science for Grade 10 learners is highly acceptable as evaluated by the identified four groups of evaluators.

Teachers should regularly evaluate the performance of Grade 10 learners in Science. The proposed printed remediation material in Science for Grade 10 learners should be recommended for use by other Grade 10 teachers in the district and the division level. Teachers should develop other forms of remediation material to address not mastered competencies. Similar studies should be conducted in Grade 10 Science focusing on other factors not included in this study.

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